

ANALYSIS OF ATTENDANCE-BASED PREDICTIVE MODEL FOR VALIDATING STUDENTS' ASSESSMENT RATINGS OF ENGINEERING TEACHERS IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: Assessment of teachers is very important in any educational institution. This is because teachers' performance influences students' behaviours in the world of work. In many institutions of higher learning, students are mandated to assess teachers through the rating of teachers' performance. However, it has been discovered that from previous ratings, variations exist among students. The variations result from regularity or truancy in attendance to school among other variables, hence, the need to understand the major factors influencing students' ratings of teachers' performance. This study identified and validated reliable evaluation criteria in ensuring accurate recognition of teachers' performance, focusing on students' attendance and key challenges amid inconsistent methods and unreliable student surveys. The study adopted exploratory visualization and correlation analysis designs making use of a predictive model for assessing the validity of Engineering teachers' performance based on students' attendance and surveys. The instrument analysed was data obtained from 5820 observations and 33 variables with key factors affecting students from Gazi University. Variables in the study were extracted, correlated and used to create a model (using linear regression) for predicting the validity of teachers' performance, which provided insight into improving teaching effectiveness. The key findings revealed that students' attendance has a high influence on their survey responses, with higher attendance correlating with a more accurate assessment of teacher's performance. Hence, students' attendance influenced the validity assessment of teacher's performance. It therefore means that filtering student surveys based on attendance could positively enhance the reliability of values obtained from students' assessments of these teachers. The study finally proposed comprehensive intervention programs to enhance student attendance, which in turn will improve the reliability and validity of teacher performance evaluations, increase the accuracy of educational assessments, and ultimately contribute to better teaching practices and improved student learning outcomes. The approach of this study provides a more reliable measure for evaluating teachers, suggesting that attendance-filtered surveys could enhance teaching practices and educational outcomes.

Keywords: assessment; performance; attendance, teachers' performance; ratings; predictive modelling; educational evaluation; engineering education

Introduction

Educational reform is very crucial when carried out based on outcomes from valid assessments, and it is expected to be a global priority, especially in improving students' outcomes and teachers' productivity. Assessment refers to the process of gathering, interpreting, and evaluating information about a learner's knowledge, skills, and attitudes for better performance. It is a systematic approach used in education and other fields to measure outcomes, guide decision-making, and inform instruction or intervention. Assessment refers to all those activities undertaken by teachers or their students in providing information to be used as feedback for modifying teaching and learning activities (Black et al., 1998). It is the process of collecting, analysing, and interpreting information to aid in decision-making (Nitko et al., 2011). In most cases, assessment is perceived as an activity performed by teachers on students, but in this study, the reverse is true, as it is the students' assessment of teachers' performance. Assessment of teachers' performance refers to a systematic evaluation of teachers' effectiveness in delivering instruction, engaging students, managing the classroom, and contributing to student learning and school improvement to provide feedback, guide professional development, and inform personnel decisions. Teachers' performance assessment also involves the evaluation of teachers' behaviours and outcomes in the classroom using a combination of observations, student achievement data, and feedback from students and their peers (Darling, 2013). Effective teacher assessment systems utilize multiple measures, such as classroom observations, student achievement data, portfolios, and student surveys, to provide a holistic view of teachers' performance. Teacher assessment is crucial for enhancing instruction, fostering professional development, and ensuring accountability in education, as it involves a structured process of rating teachers' effectiveness, providing feedback, and guiding professional growth, in addition to helping schools and their teachers to identify strengths, address weaknesses, and support the improvement of their skills for better output (Shawn et al., 2021). Assessment of teachers' performance is critical in enhancing the quality of education (Bingham et al., 1991) by monitoring and rating their performance in the school through learner interaction. The ability to distinguish between levels of performance is intended to help teachers grow and develop professionally and ultimately improve students' achievement and interest in Engineering.

Engineering is an area of study that involves the application of scientific, mathematical, and practical knowledge to invent, design, build, maintain, and improve structures, machines, devices, systems, and processes. Engineering is the application of scientific and mathematical principles to solve practical problems or the ability to identify, formulate, and solve complex engineering problems by applying principles of engineering, science, and mathematics (Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, ABET, 2022). It is the application of science to the optimum conversion of natural resources for use by humankind (Ralph, n.d). Engineers use acquired knowledge to solve real-world problems and meet societal needs in areas such as transportation, energy, healthcare, communication, and infrastructure.

At the university level, engineering has branches like Civil Engineering, which deals with the design and construction of infrastructure such as roads, bridges, and buildings; Mechanical Engineering, which deals with the design and manufacturing of mechanical systems; Electrical Engineering, which involves the design of

electrical and electronic systems; Chemical Engineering, which deals with **the** development of chemical processes for manufacturing; and Computer Engineering, which is the integration of computer science and electrical engineering to develop hardware and software. Engineering degree" is an umbrella term that covers several different types of degrees in Electrical, Chemical, Civil, Mechanical, Geotechnical, and Engineering Management (Coursera, 2025). Engineering is both a scientific discipline and a profession that balances creativity, analysis, and practical implementation. Universities offer a wide range of engineering programs, broadly categorised into core disciplines such as Civil, Chemical, Mechanical, Mechatronic, Electrical, and Electronic, and more specialised fields such as Biomedical, Computer, and Environmental Engineering.

Some universities may also offer other programs in fields like materials, aerospace, industrial, and agricultural engineering. Teachers in any of these fields are expected to teach effectively to help learners achieve the expected objectives. At the end of each academic year, teachers are assessed by their students through rating of their teachers' performance. However, it is very challenging to determine the appropriate criteria for teachers' assessment. One of the primary challenges in teachers' assessment is determining how to measure effective teaching and other behaviours (Erin, 2016). Most institutions find it very difficult to evaluate teaching due to inadequate or inaccurate facilities and the inability to utilize obtained results to directly improve teaching. This is often because effective teaching is difficult to assess, and most tools do not adequately or accurately do so without established standards. A faculty may be hesitant to change or may not be aware of the need to change their teaching practice or how to effect such change. It is necessary to develop or adopt a uniform framework defining effective teaching with appropriate tools that consider multiple facets of teaching to accommodate different approaches, modes, and environments. (Shawn et al., 2021). Various evaluation methods, which are inconsistent, have been used in the past to evaluate teachers' performance (Wei et al., 2019). One such method includes evaluating teachers' performance by teachers' skills, personal traits or teachers' ability to fulfil workplace expectations (Hassani et al., 2023). School leadership utilizes these methods in evaluating teachers' performance (Reid, 2019). Another method is the use of student evaluation surveys to provide feedback to teachers for better teaching practice. There are risks involved in relying only on such surveys to determine teachers' performance. This is because a student may have limited information and may rate a dedicated teacher poorly as the rating may be to just fill the form and not based on any sound evidence and knowledge of teachers' activities in the school (Wei et al., 2019). Although student surveys may sometimes be unreliable, they still contribute to an integral component of evaluating teachers' performance, little is known about who is best qualified to observe and evaluate teachers' performance (Lawson, 2018). Other evaluation methods for rating teachers' performance can include the use of a rubric, which expresses student development, class assessments, and reflective practices (Flowers et al., 2003). Although rubrics can also be flawed, as some students may bypass regular attendance and yet pass courses through illicit means hence, teachers who facilitate such practice cannot be deemed effective based on student development or performance (Hasiuk et al., 2023). It, therefore, means that in evaluating teachers' performance, other factors beyond students' grades and surveys should be considered. To address these problems, students' attributes and their survey assessments of teachers were analysed based on their attendance.

Attendance refers to the act of being present at a place like a school, workplace, or event. Attendance is the act of being present (Meriam, n.d). It is the presence of a student at school during official school hours (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2019). It is commonly used to track or record the presence of individuals over some time for purposes of accountability, participation, or performance. Attendance to school by a student is expected to be regular. Regular attendance refers to being present at school for the full day on all school days (NCS, 2019). Attendance helps in identifying all students who are present at classes regularly, and their responses to teachers' assessment forms could be effective in teacher evaluations (Ullah, 2020). However, both regular students and those who are not regular in school are expected to assess teachers' performance for decision-making by the administration. It is very necessary to sieve data obtained from students based on regularity of attendance to ensure reliable evaluation criteria in rewarding outstanding teachers accurately in the educational sector, hence this study. The objective of the study was to develop an attendance-based predictive model for validating students' ratings for teachers' assessment in educational sectors. Specifically, the study analysed:

1. Effects of student's attendance on other rating variables
2. Validate student's ratings based on their attendance
3. Establish optimal attendance thresholds for reliable evaluation data
4. Develop intervention strategies to improve attendance and evaluation quality

Theoretical Framework

The relationship between student attendance and evaluation validity is grounded in several educational theories. These theories are considered important and effective in supporting this research work. One of such theory is the Social Learning Theory by Bandura (1977). This theory suggests that learning occurs through observation and interaction, making physical presence essential for students to accurately assess teacher performance and their teaching effectiveness (Bandura, 1977). Students with higher attendance tend to have more opportunity to observe teaching behaviours, classroom management skills, and instructional delivery methods.

Another theory by Kearsley and Shneiderman (1998), known as the Engagement Theory, highlights that meaningful learning requires active participation and sustained interaction with educational content and instructors. Students with regular attendance are more likely to be engaged in the learning process, therefore, they are better positioned to provide informed evaluations of teaching quality.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) explains how attitudes are formed through direct experience and exposure. Students with consistent attendance develop more comprehensive attitudes toward their instructors based on repeated observations and interactions, leading to more reliable evaluation responses. Furthermore, Information Processing Theory by Goerge Miller (1985) suggests that accurate judgment requires sufficient information input. Students with poor attendance lack comprehensive exposure to teaching practices, potentially leading to evaluation bias based on limited or non-representative classroom experiences.

Data

This dataset was provided by students from Gazi University in Ankara, Turkey (Gunduz et al., 2024). The data provided was from a survey study with 28 specific questions that related to teachers' classroom activities. Each of the 28 questionnaire items was assigned a 5-point Likert scale.

The dataset has a sample size of 5820 observations with 33 variables. The variables include 28 questions (with a rating level ranging from 1 to 5). The remaining five variables were listed with a brief explanation as follows:

- **Instructors (instr):** This is the instructor's identifier with values of 1,2 and 3.
- **Class:** This includes different course codes with values of 1 to 13
- **Nb. Repeat:** The number of times a student is taking a course (values: 1,2,3,4)
- **Attendance:** This indicates the level of attendance a student has (values: 0,1,2,3,4)
- **Difficulty:** The difficulty of the course as perceived by the student (values: 1,2,3,4,5)

There was no known intervention or pre-processing of the original data from Gazi University. The questions were observed to have almost similar scores for most inputs from the students; hence, there is a need to reduce the variable number for ease of data processing. This is explained further in the method below.

Methods

Data loading and dealing with missing values: The data analysis was conducted using R programming language in RStudio software version '2023.12.1.402' (Posit Team, 2024). Due to the need for exploratory visualization of data, the **ggplot2** () library was loaded together with the **dplyr** () library for data manipulation and transformation. The data were then loaded using the **read.csv** () function. The **str** () function was used to display the structure of the dataset with a compact readable summary, including the information about data type, length and dimensions within its contents. This was performed to find out if there is a need to change the data type in each column

Missing data was checked using **sum (is.na ())** with an additional code, **drop_na** (), used to drop all missing values, if any. Data was then viewed using the **summary** () function. The **ggplot** () function was used to view the distribution of various variables, such as attendance, course difficulty, instructor, and the number of times students are taking a course. The information from the distribution was not sufficient; hence, there was a need to check the correlation between variables.

Analysing Variable Relationships and Visualization: To determine the relationships between variables and which data to start working on, the correlation of the whole dataset was viewed. The **cor**() function was used to view the correlation matrix. The **lattice::levelplot** () function was used to generate a level plot or heat maps for better visualization of the matrix.

Variable Reduction: The dataset variables were reduced after analysing the relationship existing between them. Since the questionnaire items were all correlated with a similar value across all columns of Q1 to Q28 by observation, the mean of the selected row was then calculated using the **rowMeans**() function. The calculated mean was saved into a new dataset using the piping function (**%>%**). The new dataset with the mean score which

was created helped in preserving the theoretical dimensions of the teaching effectiveness. The mean was then arranged in three levels (High, Medium, and Low) with the help of the **quantile ()** function, with theoretical justification based on normal distribution assumptions and educational assessment standards. **The mutate()** function in the **dplyr** library that was loaded earlier was utilized together with piping to add a new column signifying students' ratings of teachers with a high, medium, or low score, replaced with the calculated mean, and the summary was viewed using the **head()** function. A new correlation table was then generated with the same relationship between the other variables, with little or no change in matrix values.

Impact of Attendance and Data Filtering: An analysis was carried out to analyse the relationships between different data variables using the **ggplot ()** function. After the analysis, further data filtering and manipulation were carried out to eliminate unwanted variables using the **filter ()** and **select ()** functions in the **dplyr** library. Piping was used in creating a new dataset and imputing the new data. The final data was viewed and analysed after data tidying.

Visualization and Interpretation: The new data was then analysed to check the effect of the changes carried out using the piping function (**%>%**) with other functions (**group_by()**, **summarize()**, and **mutate()**). This helped to generate a table (data frame) to view the percentage change, comparing the old and new data. The **ggplot()** function was also used to view the percentage change in a pie chart to understand the factors that could be used to rate and evaluate teachers' performance. A new final data was created using the piping, **mutate ()** and **case_when()** functions to assign validity to students' evaluation of their teachers' performance.

Linear Regression Model: The final step was the creation of a linear model for predicting the validity of students' evaluation and ranking teachers' performance based on evaluation values. To do this effect, the validity of their evaluation was assigned to different numbers, with 0 meaning non-valid and 4 meaning strongly valid. This was performed using the **piping** and **mutate ()** functions. Next, values of the validity were removed at random and replaced with **NA**. The **lm ()** function with its syntax for the argument was utilized in producing a linear regression model between row mean and students' attendance. Finally, the values of **NA** were replaced by the model by utilizing the **predict ()** function and the result value compared with the initial validity analysis.

In summary, to gain insights into the distribution and relationships between various variables, the exploratory data analysis (EDA) technique was applied. A linear regression model was then adopted to evaluate students' responses and predict teachers' performance based on the attendance variable.

Results and Discussion

After loading the dataset, missing data were checked, and none was found. The data type of different columns was also checked, and all were numeric; hence, there was no need for data type conversion since only numerical data values in the initial step of the analysis were needed. For exploratory visualization, the data distribution was plotted using a bar chart in **ggplot**, and the graphs in Fig. 4a, 4b and 4c found in the appendix, were obtained. The information from the data distribution was not enough to understand the data distribution hence, the correlation between various columns was calculated to understand the relationship between variables. The result as shown in Fig. 1a was obtained.

Fig. 1a: Unfiltered data correlation matrix

Fig. 1b: Filtered data correlation matrix

The correlation matrix showed that the questionnaire items were related, while the next highest correlation value was the attendance variable. This showed that the questions answered by individual students were more affected by their attendance in class rather than the difficulty, instructor, or number of times the course has been taken.

The next step was to reduce the variables, and to do this, the data set was further analysed based on the relationship between questions answered. All questions answered by the student, from Q1 to Q28, had a very strong relationship, and from analysing the data set, it was clear that each student gave a similar score for all questions; hence, their mean was calculated and added into a new column. The correlation matrix of that new data set was calculated and displayed in Fig. 1b. The matrix maintained a similar colour code across variables with the attendance still having a stronger relationship with the new calculated row mean. The row mean, which was assigned high, medium and low and saved in a new column named ‘Tp’ (teachers’ performance) is shown in Table 1. To analyse the effect of attendance on other variables, the bar plot between variables was plotted and shown in Fig. 2a, and 2b.

Table 1: Dataset Containing Teachers Performance (Tp) Ratings

Id	Instr	Class	Nb.repeat	Attendance	Difficulty	Row mean	Tp
1	1	2	1	0	4	3	Medium
2	1	2	1	1	3	3	Medium
3	1	2	1	2	4	5	High
4	1	2	1	1	3	3	Medium
5	1	2	1	0	1	1	Low

Fig. 2a: Attendance vs Tp

Fig. 2b: Attendance vs Course difficulty

In Fig. 2a, students with low attendance levels rated most teachers' performance as low. In the same way, Fig. 2b showed that most students with 0 attendance level gave a difficulty level of 1, which seems odd compared to the rating of other students with higher attendance. In this effect, students' ratings with 0 and 1 levels of attendance affected teachers' performance rating and hence need to be filtered out of the data set, as with the results shown in Fig. 3a and 3b.

Fig. 3a: Attendance vs Tp (Filtered)

Fig. 3b: Attendance vs Course difficulty (Filtered)

The teachers' performance rating and difficulty rating across attendance levels 2, 3 and 4 look more balanced and acceptable in determining teachers' performance. To further support this, the number of times a course was taken by students from the old data, and the new filtered data were plotted using a pie chart with the percentage displayed in Fig. 5a and 5b, in the appendix. The old data showed that 84.3% of students took the course just once, while the new data showed that 88.4% of students took the course once, showing a percentage increase in students' performance. In the same effect, there was a reduction in the percentage of students retaking the course more than once. Fig. 6a and 6b also displayed the percentage increase in the teachers' performance after the filtering.

Furthermore, the new column added displayed the validity of the student's ratings based on their attendance. Various values of the column were eliminated, and the trained linear model was used in predicting the values of the missing data. The previous data with missing data and the predicted result are shown in Table 2 and Table 3

Table 2: Dataset to be modelled, containing NA.

Id	Instr	Class	Nb.repeat	Attendance	Difficulty	Rowmean	Tp	Validity	Tp_n
1	1	2	1	0	4	3	M	NV	0
2	1	2	1	1	3	3	M	MV	1
3	1	2	1	2	4	5	H	MV	2
4	1	2	1	1	3	3	M	MV	NA
5	1	2	1	0	1	1	L	NV	0
6	1	2	1	3	3	4	M	SV	NA

Table 3: Prediction of the Validity of Teachers' Performance

Id	Instr	Class	Nb.repeat	Attendance	Difficulty	Rowmean	Tp	Validity	Tp_n
1	1	2	1	0	4	3	M	NV	0
2	1	2	1	1	3	3	M	MV	1
3	1	2	1	2	4	5	H	MV	2
4	1	2	1	1	3	3	M	MV	1
5	1	2	1	0	1	1	L	NV	0
6	1	2	1	3	3	4	M	SV	3

Fig. 4a: Instructors distribution

Fig. 4b: Attendance Distribution

Fig. 4c: Nb.repeat distribution

Distribution of nb.repeat Categories in Original Data

Distribution of nb.repeat Categories in Filtered Data

Fig. 5a: Nb.repeat pie chart of original data

Fig. 5b: Nb.repeat pie chart of filtered data

Distribution of Teacher performance Categories in Original Data

Fig. 6a: Tp pie chart of original data

Distribution of Teacher performance Categories in Filtered Data

Fig. 6b: Tp pie chart of filtered data

Proposed Interventions for Attendance Improvement

To address variations in student attendance that could impact evaluation validity, this study recommends implementing the following evidence-based interventions:

To address variations in student attendance that could impact the validity of educational evaluations, this study recommends implementing the following evidence-based interventions designed to improve student attendance while maintaining academic rigor.

Technology-Enhanced Engagement Strategies

The integration of technology in educational settings has demonstrated significant potential for enhancing student engagement and motivation to attend classes. Interactive polling systems and real-time feedback tools serve as powerful mechanisms to increase student participation by creating lively, responsive learning environments that encourage active involvement rather than passive consumption of information (Smith & Johnson, 2023). These technological interventions transform traditional lectures into interactive experiences where students become active contributors to the learning process.

Additionally, the integration of collaborative learning activities specifically requires physical presence which further reinforces the value of attendance. Group projects, peer evaluations, and team-based problem-solving exercises create interdependencies among students that naturally encourage consistent attendance (Davis & Wilson, 2024). These activities cannot be replicated through remote participation, making physical presence both necessary and rewarding.

Attendance Incentive Programs

Although intrinsic motivation remains the ideal driver for attendance, a well-designed incentive programs can provide additional support for students struggling with attendance consistency. Participation grades that reward consistent attendance, while carefully avoiding penalties for legitimate absences, create a balanced approach that recognizes the value of presence without discriminating against students facing genuine barriers (Thompson & Lee, 2023). This approach requires careful policy design to distinguish between voluntary and involuntary absences.

Bonus point systems for students maintaining high attendance rates offer positive reinforcement that can motivate behaviour change without creating punitive consequences. Research indicates that reward-based systems tend to be more effective than penalty-based approaches in promoting sustained behavioural change (Martinez & Garcia, 2022). Recognition programs for consistent attendees, whether through certificates, public acknowledgment, or other forms of positive reinforcement, can create social incentives that support attendance improvement efforts.

Flexible Learning Support Systems

Acknowledging that some students face certain barriers to consistent attendance, flexible learning support systems provide necessary alternatives while maintaining educational standards. Hybrid learning options for students with known attendance difficulty acknowledge that various circumstances, including work obligations, family responsibilities, or health issues, may impact attendance patterns (Anderson & White, 2024). These systems provide alternative pathways to learning while preserving the core educational objectives.

The provision of recorded lectures for makeup learning, combined with maintained attendance requirements for evaluation participation, creates a safety net that supports learning continuity without compromising the importance of physical presence during assessments and evaluations (Taylor et al., 2023). This approach recognizes the distinction between content delivery and evaluation participation, ensuring that assessment validity is maintained while supporting student learning needs.

Early Warning Systems

Proactive identification and intervention represent crucial components of effective attendance improvement strategies. Automated attendance tracking systems with early intervention protocols for affected students enable timely support that can prevent minor attendance issues from becoming major obstacles to academic success (Phillips & Kumar, 2024). These systems can identify patterns and trends that might not be immediately apparent to instructors.

Faculty notification systems for sudden attendance drops create opportunities for immediate intervention and support. When instructors are alerted to significant changes in student attendance patterns, they can reach out to students to identify potential issues and connect them with appropriate resources (Evans & Miller, 2023). This proactive approach demonstrates institutional care for student success while providing opportunities for early problem resolution.

The integration of student support services for attendance-related issues ensures that identified problems are addressed through appropriate channels. By connecting attendance tracking systems with counselling services, financial aid offices, and other student support resources, institutions can provide comprehensive assistance that addresses the root causes of attendance problems (Green & Adams, 2024).

Implementation Considerations and Future Directions

The successful implementation of attendance improvement interventions requires careful consideration of institutional context, student demographics, and available resources. Institutions must balance the goal of improving attendance with respect for student autonomy and recognition of legitimate barriers to participation. Additionally, the effectiveness of these interventions should be regularly evaluated through systematic data

collection and analysis to ensure they are achieving their intended outcomes without creating unintended negative consequences.

Future research should focus on the long-term effectiveness of these interventions across different institutional types, student populations, and academic disciplines. Understanding how attendance improvement strategies interact with other factors affecting student success will help institutions develop more targeted and effective approaches to supporting student engagement and learning outcomes.

Conclusion

This report analysed the critical role of student attendance in evaluating teachers' performance by reducing the complexity of initial variables and focusing on key factors that are correlated. The findings suggest that students' surveys, when filtered for attendance, provided a more reliable measure of teachers' performance hence, a need to create a linear model for predicting the validity of student's ratings on teachers' performances for a similar dataset. This prediction model can be improved by introducing and training more variables with a strong relation with the questions answered, which can be used in highlighting key areas for improvement in teaching methods and strategies to adopt in engaging the students more. The study also proposed interventions to improve the student's attendance which addresses both the symptoms and underlying causes of attendance variations. By combining technology-enhanced engagement strategies, thoughtfully designed incentive programs, flexible support systems, and proactive early warning mechanisms, educational institutions can create environments that naturally encourage attendance while providing necessary support for students facing barriers. The success of these interventions depends on careful implementation, ongoing evaluation, and adaptation to specific institutional contexts and student populations.

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Appendix A (RStudio Code)

```
library(dplyr);library(ggplot2) # This Loads necessary libraries needed in this code
data = read.csv("Downloads/Data 14/Teachers_performance.csv") # Loading the csv file
#Structure of the dataset, check missing values and summarise data
str(data); sum(is.na(data)); summary(data)
data <- data %>% # This removes missing values if any
  drop_na()
ggplot(data, aes(x = instr)) + # Distribution of instructors
  geom_bar(fill = "brown") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of instructor", x = "Instructor", y = "Count")
ggplot(data, aes(x = attendance)) + # Distribution of attendance
  geom_bar(fill = "brown") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of Attendance", x = "Attendance Code", y = "Count")
ggplot(data_5, aes(x = nb.repeat)) + # Distribution of number of times a course is taken
  geom_bar(fill = "brown") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of nb.repeat", x = "nb.repeat", y = "Count")
cor_matrix = cor(data[, ]); cor_matrix # Calculate correlation matrix
lattice::levelplot(cor_matrix, # Plotting correlation matrix
  main = "Correlation Matrix Heat Map",
  xlab = list(rot = 0), # Rotating x-labels by 90 degrees
  scales = list(x = list(rot = 90))) # Keeping ticks horizontal
#storing data into a new data (data_!), #column selection for mean calculation
data_1=data; selected_columns = data_1[,6:33]
data_2 = data_1 %>% # Calculating row means for the selected columns
  mutate(row_mean = rowMeans(select(., 6:33), na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  select(-Q1:-Q28)
cutoffs = quantile(data_2$row_mean, probs = c(0.25, 0.5, 0.75)) #calculating cutoff points for the row mean
```

```
print(cutoffs) #prints the cutoff points
data_3 = data_2 %>% #Creating a new variable that binds it to the original dataset.labels low, medium, and high
of the cutoff points
mutate(Tp = case_when(
row_mean <= cutoffs[1] ~ "Low",
row_mean > cutoffs[1] & row_mean <= cutoffs[3] ~ "Medium",
row_mean > cutoffs[3] ~ "High",))
head(data_3) # Displaying the first few rows of the updated data frame
cor_matrix <- cor(data_3[,1:6]); cor_matrix # Calculating the correlation matrix for the Q1-Q28 questions
lattice::levelplot(cor_matrix, # Plotting the correlation matrix
xlab = list(rot = 0), # Rotating x-labels by 90 degrees
scales = list(x = list(rot = 90))) # Keeping ticks horizontal
data_4=data_3 #creating a mirror data of data_3
factor_columns = c("instr", "class", "attendance", "difficulty", "Tp") #Factor type conversion
data_4[factor_columns] = lapply(data_4[factor_columns], as.factor)
ggplot(data_4, aes(x = instr, fill = Tp)) + # Relationship between instructor and teachers performance
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
  labs(title = "Instructor vs teachers performance", x = "Instructor", y = "Proportion", fill = "teachers
performance")
ggplot(data_4, aes(x = attendance, fill = Tp)) + # Relationship btw attendance and Tp
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
  labs(title = "Attendance vs Teachers Performance", x = "attendance", y = "Proportion", fill = "teachers
performance")
ggplot(data_4, aes(x = attendance, fill = difficulty)) + # Relationship between attendance and course difficulty
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
  labs(title = "Attendance vs Course Difficulty", x = "attendance", y = "Proportion", fill = "difficulty")
data_5 = data_3 %>% # Removing rows with lower attendance value
  filter(!attendance %in% c(0,1)) %>%
  select(-class)
factor_columns <- c("instr", "attendance", "difficulty", "Tp") #Factor type conversion
data_5[factor_columns] <- lapply(data_5[factor_columns], as.factor)
ggplot(data_5, aes(x = instr, fill = Tp)) + # Relationship between instructor and teachers performance
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
  labs(title = "Instructor vs Course Difficulty", x = "Instructor", y = "Proportion", fill = "teachers performance")
ggplot(data_5, aes(x = attendance, fill = Tp)) + # Relationship between attendance and teachers performance
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
```

```
labs(title = "Attendance vs teachers performance", x = "attendance", y = "Proportion", fill = "teachers
performance")
ggplot(data_5, aes(x = attendance, fill = difficulty)) + # Relationship between attendance and course difficulty
  geom_bar(position = "fill") +
  labs(title = "attendance vs Course Difficulty", x = "attendance", y = "Proportion", fill = "difficulty")
category_counts = data_3 %>% # calculating percentage change in the teachers' performance
  group_by(Tp) %>%
  summarize(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(percentage = count / sum(count) * 100)
category_counts_1 = data_5 %>%
  group_by(Tp) %>%
  summarize(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(percentage = count / sum(count) * 100)
print(category_counts); print(category_counts_1) # Print counts and percentages of category.
category_counts_2 = data %>% # calculating the percentage change in the number of times a course is taken
  group_by(nb.repeat) %>%
  summarize(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(percentage = count / sum(count) * 100)
category_counts_3 = data_5 %>%
  group_by(nb.repeat) %>%
  summarize(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(percentage = count / sum(count) * 100)
print(category_counts_2); print(category_counts_3) # Print the counts and percentages of each category
ggplot(category_counts_2, aes(x = "", y = percentage, fill = as.factor(nb.repeat))) + # Create pie chart for
`category_counts_2`
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of nb.repeat Categories in Original Data",
fill = "nb.repeat") +
theme_void() + # Removes the background and axes
geom_text(aes(label = paste0(round(percentage, 1), "%")),
position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5))
ggplot(category_counts_3, aes(x = "", y = percentage, fill = as.factor(nb.repeat))) + # Create pie chart for
`category_counts_3`
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y") +
```

```
labs(title = "Distribution of nb.repeat Categories in Filtered Data",
fill = "nb.repeat") +
  theme_void() + # Removes the background and axes
  geom_text(aes(label = paste0(round(percentage, 1), "%")),
position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5))
ggplot(category_counts, aes(x = "", y = percentage, fill = as.factor(Tp))) + # Create pie chart for `category_counts`
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of Teachers performance Categories in Original Data",
fill = "Teachers performance") +
  theme_void() + # Removes the background and axes
  geom_text(aes(label = paste0(round(percentage, 1), "%")),
position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5))
ggplot(category_counts_1, aes(x = "", y = percentage, fill = as.factor(Tp))) + # Create pie chart for
`category_counts_1`
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y") +
  labs(title = "Distribution of Teachers performance Categories in Filtered Data",
fill = "Teachers performance") +
  theme_void() + # Removes the background and axes
  geom_text(aes(label = paste0(round(percentage, 1), "%")),
position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5))
data_7 = data_3 %>% # Create a new column 'validity' based on the 'attendance' values
  mutate(validity = case_when(
    attendance == 0 ~ "Not Valid",
    attendance == 1 ~ "Moderately Valid",
    attendance == 2 ~ "Moderately Valid",
    attendance == 3 ~ "Strongly Valid",
    attendance == 4 ~ "Strongly Valid"))
data_8 = data_7 %>% #Creating a mirror data and adding a new column
  mutate(tp_n = attendance)
indices_to_replace = seq(4, nrow(data_8), by = 2); data_8$tp_n[indices_to_replace] = NA # Generating indices
for every 2th value and replacing with NA
model = lm(tp_n ~ row_mean + attendance, data = data_8) # Creating a linear model
data_10=data_8 #Replacing NA values with the predicted value of the linear model
I=is.na(data_10$tp_n);data_10$tp_n[I]=round(predict(model,newdata=data_10[I,]))
head(data_10)
```